

Potentiometric Studies on the Ternary Complex Systems : Metal(II)-Salicylic Acid-Amino Acids

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Ternary complex systems, metal(II)-salicylic acid derivatives (as primary ligands)-acidic and basic amino acids (as secondary ligands) have been investigated by the potentiometric technique. Formation constant values of the various binary and ternary complexes liable to exist in such systems have been determined at 25° and $\mu=0.2$ mol dm⁻³ (KCl). The order of stability of the binary or ternary complexes in terms of nature of the metal ion salicylic acid derivative and amino acid as well as the stability of the ternary complex is compared to that of the binary amino acid complex.

Due to the biological importance of both salicylic acid derivatives and amino acids, considerable interest has been shown concerning transition metal ions ternary complexes containing each of these two ligands with numerous N or N,N or N,O or O,O donor ligands. However, little information is available concerning the formation constants of the ternary systems containing the two competing ligands, amino acids and salicylic acids¹⁻³. Martin and Paris¹ analysed the data from pH-titration of the aqueous mixture of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II}-glycinate-5-sulphosalicylate. Gerbeleu and Shenderovskayer² studied the mixed ligand complexes of the system Fe^{III}-salicylate- α -amino acid spectrophotometrically. Migal *et al.*³ investigated the effect of substituent of α -aminobutyric acids on the stability of the mixed ligand Cu^{II} complexes of the salicylate and sulphosalicylate series in aqueous solutions. It was proved that the stability of the complex decreases with the introduction of OH and S substituents into α -aminobutyric acid.

Accordingly, in this communication, a systematic study on the complex formation between some divalent transition metal ions Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, salicylic acid derivatives H₂SAD (3,5-dinitro-, 5-sulpho- and thiosalicylic acid, 3,5-DNSA, 5-SSA, TSA respectively) as primary ligands and acidic and basic amino acids as (L-serine, L-proline, L-threonine, L-aspartic and L-asparagine, L-glutamine and L-lysine respectively) as secondary ligands in aqueous media has been carried out using the potentiometric technique. The formation constants of the binary and ternary metal complexes have been determined adopting the Irving and Rossotti technique⁴. The aim of the present work is to determine the formation constant values of the different binary and ternary complexes formed in such systems. The stability of the ternary complexes has been examined and discussed in relation to that of the corresponding binary complexes as well as in terms of nature of metal ion, salicylic acid derivative and amino acid moieties.

Results and Discussion

Identical titration curves are obtained for the different ternary systems under investigation according to the sequence described in the experimental section. Representative curves are displayed in Figs. 1 and 2. Examination of the curves for the 1 : 1 binary M(II)-SAD complex solutions reveals that these complexes are formed at lower pH's (5.1-6.3, 4.1-6.0 and 2.6-4.5 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively). This is attained from the appeared divergence of each of the titration curve of the binary complex solution (curve c) from the corresponding free SAD one (curve b). It is worthy to indicate that the binary complex solutions of Cu^{II} with 3,5-DNSA or TSA show precipitates at pH ~10. This can be likely ascribed to the behaviour that these complexes undergo hydrolysis reaction where hydroxo complex species are probably formed. Accordingly in such cases a further study

Fig. 1. Titration curves for [Cu^{II}-3,5-DNSA-aspartic acid] system at 25° and at $\mu=0.2$ mol dm⁻³ with 0.2145 mol dm⁻³ NaOH

Fig. 2. Titration curves for [Ni^{II}-TSA-proline] system at 25° and $\mu=0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ with $0.2145 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ NaOH.

was not possible beyond the precipitation point in each case. On the other hand, the titration curves of the different M(II)-amino acid binary complex solutions reveal that these complexes begin to form in the pH ranges 5.6–7.5, 3.5–6.0 and 3.2–4.5 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively.

With respect to the titration curves of the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes, one deduces that these titration curves strongly overlap with the titration curves of the 1 : 1 binary M(II)-SAD at lower pH's (curves f and c). This suggests that in the lower pH's where the formation of M(II)-SAD complex takes place, the amino acid does not combine with M(II). Generally, at higher pH's, one observes a divergence of the ternary titration curve from the corresponding binary M(II)-SAD one. The pH value at which divergence occurred is largely dependent on the nature of both the metal ion and the two ligands (pH 2.8–7.0, 3.2–6.0, 3.5–8.0 in case of Co^{II}-5-SSA, -3,5-DNSA, -TSA, 2.7–5.4, 3.0–5.0, 2.9–5.2 in case of Ni^{II}-5-SSA, -3,5-DNSA, -TSA and 2.5–3.7, 3.0–3.2, 2.6–6.0 in case of Cu^{II}-5-SSA, -3,5-DNSA, -TSA, respectively). This behaviour reveals that the coordination of amino acid with the binary M(II)-SAD takes place in stepwise manner,

where, $x = -1$ for monocarboxylic amino acids and $x = -2$ for dicarboxylic aspartic acid.

Thus, it may be assumed that amino acid would combine with M(II)-SAD binary complex species in ternary systems similarly as it does with $[M(H_2O)_6]^{2+}$ binary system. In this respect it is worthy to indicate that except in the case of Cu(II)-TSA binary complex, the other binary $[M(SAD)]$ complexes are quite stable up to the pH range where the attachment of amino acid takes place forming

the ternary complex. Thus one can easily deduce that the different metal ternary complexes under investigation are formed before hydrolysing pHs of the corresponding binary $[M(SAD)]$ complexes. However for all ternary metal complex solutions studied, precipitation occurred in the case of the systems Ni^{II}-5-SSA-proline, Cu^{II}-5-SSA-threonine, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}-3,5-DNSA-proline, Ni^{II}-3,5-DNSA-asparagine, glutamine and Cu^{II}-3,5-DNSA-monocarboxylic amino acids. Thus beyond the precipitation point for each of these ternary systems, further study was not possible, hence the hydroxo species likely to be formed after this stage could not be studied. The observed very weak tendency of Cu^{II}-TSA binary complex to undergo reaction with each of the amino acids under investigation can be ascribed to the tendency of this complex to undergo hydrolysis reaction (i.e. formation of hydroxo species at pH lower than that suitable for the coordination of the amino acid).

The acid dissociation constants for all SAD and amino acids were determined under identical conditions from the titration curves a, b and a, d respectively, making use of the Irving and Rossotti formulate⁴. The values obtained for 5-SSA, 3,5-DNSA, TSA and aa are in good agreement with the corresponding ones reported in the literature⁵⁻⁹. It is worth mentioning that pK_{a1} value for all amino acids studied are too low (≤ 2.0 and exist only in strongly acid solutions). Accordingly these values are not used in the calculation of the binary or ternary complex formation constants.

Formation constants values: The horizontal distance between curves c and f can be measured and used for the calculation of \bar{n}_{mix} (average number of secondary ligand amino acid molecules associated with one $[M(SAD)]$). The equation used for the calculation of \bar{n}_{mix} will be the same as the original paper⁴,

$$\bar{n}_{mix} = \frac{(V_t - V_0)[N^0 + E^0 + T_L^0(Y - \bar{n}_H)]}{(V_0 + V_t) \bar{n}_H T_M^0} \quad (1)$$

where T_M^0 is the concentration of M(II) used, Y the number of dissociable protons of amino acid, V_0 the original volume (50 ml) and V_0 and V_t are the volumes of alkali consumed to reach the same pH values in curves c and f. All other symbols have their usual meaning⁴. \bar{n}_H for the secondary ligand, amino acid at different pH values were available from determination of the amino acids formation constants values as described above. From the values of \bar{n}_{mix} so obtained, free secondary ligand exponent, pL'_{mix} was calculated using the equation,

$$pL'_{mix} = \log \left(\sum_{y=0}^{y=1 \text{ or } 2} \frac{\beta_y^H \cdot (1/10^B)^y}{T_L - \bar{n}_{mix} T_M^0} \cdot \frac{V_0 + V_t}{V_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, β_y^H is the second and third formation constant values for the applying amino acids, and B the pH-meter reading.

Fig. 3. Experimental formation curves for the ternary 1 : 1 : 1 Ni(II)-5-SSA-amino acids complexes (\bar{n}_{mix} - pL) at 25° and $\mu=0.2$ mol dm⁻³ KCl: (a) serine, (b) threonine, (c) aspartic, (d) asparagine, (e) glutamine and (f) lysine.

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANT VALUES OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES

Ligand	log K_{SAD}^M or log $K_{M(aa)}^M$			log $K_{M(SAD)(aa)}^M$										
	CoII	NiII	CuII	CoII			NiII			CuII				
				3,5-DNSA	5-SSA	TSA	3,5-DNSA	5-SSA	TSA	3,5-DNSA	5-SSA	TSA		
3,5-DNSA	3.40	3.60	6.00											
5-SSA	6.20	7.18	8.75											
TSA	6.20	7.75	18.20											
Serine	4.40	5.80	8.10	4.80	4.00	4.10	5.20	5.60	5.20	—	—	7.80	—	—
Threonine	5.00	5.70	7.40	4.20	8.70	4.00	5.60	5.10	4.50	—	—	—	—	—
Proline	5.40	6.25	9.00	—	4.20	8.50	—	—	4.40	—	—	8.60	—	—
Aspartic	5.45	7.00	8.80	8.60	9.85	8.90	9.30	9.40	9.80	9.40	9.60	9.60	—	—
Asparagine	4.70	5.10	8.00	4.50	4.20	3.80	—	4.80	4.90	—	—	7.80	—	—
Glutamine	4.40	5.20	7.90	4.30	4.10	3.80	—	4.60	4.80	—	—	7.80	—	—
Lysine	5.00	5.80	10.00	4.70	4.40	4.90	4.53	4.60	5.70	—	—	4.20	—	—

Formation curves corresponding to the various mixed ligand M(II)-SAD-aa systems were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_{mix} vs pL'_{mix} (representative results are shown in Fig. 3). The corresponding formation constants $\log K_{M(SAD)(aa)}^M$ obtained by the average value method are reported in Table 1. For comparison of the stability of the M(II)-SAD-aa ternary complex with that of the binary M(II)-SAD or M(II)-aa, the formation constants of the different binary complexes were determined. This was made by applying the original equations of Irving and Rossotti⁴ to the binary complex solutions systems (curves b, c and d, e for M(II)-SAD and -aa respectively). The various $\log K_{M(SAD)}^M$ and $\log K_{M(aa)}^M$ values obtained from the experimental formation curves of the binary complex systems by the average value method are reported in Table 1. Some of these values are in good agreement with those found in the literature⁵. Examination of the formation constant values for the complexes studied in terms of nature of each of the

three constituents reveals the following important conclusions.

(i) The stability of the different 1:1 binary M(II)-SAD complexes increases according to the order: 3,5-DNSA < 5-SSA < TSA. This can be interpreted in terms of the effect of basicity of these compounds since the PK_{a1} and PK_{a2} values of 3,5-DNSA are low relative to the corresponding ones of 5-SSA and TSA (pK_{COOH} and pK_{OH} for 3,5-DNSA and 5-SSA are 1.31, 7.0⁶ and 2.49, 12⁶ respectively and pK_{COOH} and PK_{SH} for TSA are 5.44 and 9.52^{7,8}). Furthermore, the presence of high electron withdrawing groups (two NO₂ in 3,5-DNSA and SO₃H in 5-SSA) reflects their self in low stability of the complexes containing these ligands. On the other hand, the possibility of M→Sπ interaction in the case of M(TSA) complex is expected to play a significant role in increasing stability of the such complex.

